

Development And Evaluation of Anti-Dandruff Herbal Hair Pack

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ABSTRACT:

Dandruff is a prevalent scalp disorder characterized by flaking, itching, and irritation primarily associated with microbial and fungal growth. Continuous use of synthetic anti-dandruff product may cause adverse effect leading to interest in herbal formulation. The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate anti-dandruff herbal hair pack using *Azadirachta indica* (neem) leaves and *Trigonella foenum-graecum* (fenugreek) seeds. The herbal hair pack was prepared using neem powder, fenugreek powder, multani mitti, rose water, glycerine, vitamin E, and lavender oil. Phytochemical screening of plant materials confirmed the presence of bioactive constituents such as carbohydrate, flavanoids, alkaloids, tannins, saponins, and triterpenoids. The formulated hair pack is evaluated for physicochemical parameters including organoleptic properties, pH, viscosity, spreadability, washability. All the formulation exhibited acceptable pH values, spreadability, and easy washability. In-vitro antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* demonstrated significant zone of inhibition, indicating effective antimicrobial potential. The result suggested that developed anti-dandruff herbal hair pack is safe, stable, and effective in managing dandruff and maintain scalp health.

KEYWORDS:

Anti-dandruff, neem, herbal hair pack, fenugreek, anti-microbial, anti-fungal.

INTRODUCTION:

As per the Drugs and Cosmetic act 1940 and rules 1945, Cosmetic means any article intended to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled or sprayed on, or introduced into, or otherwise applied to, the human body or any part thereof for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness and includes any article intended for use as a component of cosmetic.

Herbal cosmetics can be defined as the products, which possess desirable physiological activity like healing, enhancement of appearance, and conditioning properties due to the presence of herbal ingredients present in it. Herbal cosmetics mainly include herbs either in crude form or in form of extract. The basics of cosmetics used in skin care are taken from ancient texts of Rigveda, Yajurveda, and various systems of medicines like Ayurveda, Unani and Homeopathic. In the present time, safe and elegant cosmetic products are developed by merging the knowledge and experience of herbs and cosmetic technology, which is widely accepted amongst the masses. In true means it can be said to be blend of nature with modern technology.

HAIR:

Hair is simple in structure made of root and shaft. The hair root is enclosed in the hair follicle, submerges into the skin in inclination and ends down to the bulb while hair shaft is the part of the hair seen above the skin. Hair

is made up of tough protein called keratin that forms the strength of the hair. Keratin is a large molecule made up of smaller units called amino acids, which join together to form a chain. Hair structure is made up of different layers and structures. Usually, hair consist of two parts follicle and shaft. The hair follicle is the centre of the biological activity like hair growth, pigmentation; whereas the hair shaft is considered to be dead and is mainly made of protein.

DANDRUFF:

Dandruff is a common scalp disorder characterized by excessive shedding of dead skin cells from the scalp. It often appears as white or yellowish flakes on the hair and shoulders and may be accompanied by itching, irritation or redness of the scalp. Dandruff is not a serious condition, but it can be uncomfortable and embarrassing for those affected. The main cause of dandruff includes overgrowth of the yeast, *Malassezia furfur*, excessive oil production (seborrhoea), poor scalp hygiene stress, hormonal imbalance, and use of unsuitable hair products. Environmental factors such as pollution and weather changes can also worsen dandruff. There are two types of dandruff: dry dandruff, which occurs due to a dry scalp and leads to fine, loose flakes, and oily dandruff, which is caused by excess sebum, leading to sticky, yellowish flakes that cling to the scalp. Dandruff can be managed through proper scalp care, balanced diet, and use of medicated or herbal anti-dandruff formulations that have antifungal, antibacterial, and soothing properties.

HAIR PACK:

A Hair Pack is a semisolid topical preparation applied to the scalp and hair to improve hair health, scalp condition and overall appearance. It is formulated using a combination of herbal powders, clays, oils, conditioners, humectants, and therapeutic plant extracts. Hair packs have been used since ancient times in Ayurvedic, Unani, and traditional cosmetic systems for their nourishing, cleansing, conditioning, and therapeutic effects on the hair and scalp.

COMPONENTS OF HAIR PACK

1) Herbal Active Ingredient

These are the main ingredients that provide therapeutic action.

Anti-dandruff Herbs:

- Neem (*Azadirachta indica*): Strong Antifungal, Antibacterial
- Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum graceum*): Anti-dandruff, Soothing

2) Base / Bulk Forming Agents

These helps form the structure of the pack.

- Multani Mitti: absorbs excess of oil, gives smooth consistency

3) Antioxidant agent

Plays important role in maintaining healthy hair.

- Vitamin E: fat soluble antioxidant

4) Excipients/ Additives

These improve stability, appearances and usability of the hair pack

- Preservatives: sodium benzoate.
- Fragrance: lavender oil.

5) Liquid Medium

Used for making paste at the time of application.

- Rose water

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Table 1: List of Materials used for preparation of herbal hair pack

SL.NO	List of materials	Role
1	Neem powder	Antifungal agent
2	Fenugreek powder	Natural conditioner
3	Multani mitti	Cleansing and absorbent
4	Sodium benzoate	Preservative
5	Vitamin E	Antioxidant agent
6	Lavender oil	Fragrance
7	Rose water	Vehicle and soothing agent
8	Glycerine	Humectant
9	Distilled water	Solvent

COLLECTION OF PLANT MATERIALS

Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*) and fresh leaves of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) was collected from our native place.

AUTHENTIFICATION OF PLANT MATERIALS

Collected plants that are Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*) and fresh leaves of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) was authenticated by Dr Dintu K.P, Assistant Professor, Department of Botany Fathima Mata College, Kollam.

DRYING & POWDERING OF PLANT MATERIALS

The collected plant materials such as Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*) and fresh leaves of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) was dried. Then, it was powdered to increase the surface area and sieved through sieve no 80 and separated as fine and coarse powder.

PREPARATION OF DECOCTION

Preparation of *Trigonella foenum-graecum* and *Azadirachta indica* decoction:

Weigh 10g of the powdered plant material. Add it to the beaker containing 100ml of distilled water. Heat gently and boil for 15-20 minutes. Allow the mixture to cool to room temperature. Filter using filter paper.

FORMULATION OF HERBAL HAIR PACK

The required quantities of neem powder, fenugreek powder, and multani mitti were accurately weighed and passed through appropriate sieve. The powders were mixed uniformly in a mortar. Sodium benzoate was dissolved separately in a small quantity of distilled water and added to the powder mixture. Rose water, glycerin and the remaining distilled water were added gradually with continuous trituration to obtain a smooth paste. Vitamin E was incorporated into the mixture with gentle stirring. Lavender oil was added at the final stage for fragrance. The prepared hair pack transferred into a suitable, well-labeled container.

Table 2: Formulation of herbal hair pack

SL NO	INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3
1	Neem powder	2.5g	4g	1.8g
2	Fenugreek powder	2.5g	4g	1.8g
3	Multani Mitti	9.4g	7.3g	11.2g
4	Sodium benzoate	0.25g	0.25g	0.25g
5	Vitamin E	0.25ml	0.25ml	0.25ml
6	Lavender oil	0.1ml	0.1ml	0.1ml
7	Rose water	Qs	Qs	Qs
8	Glycerine	0.6ml	0.7ml	0.5ml
9	Distilled water	4.4ml	3.4ml	4.1ml

EVALUATION OF HERBAL HAIR PACK

Formulated hair pack was evaluated for organoleptic properties such as color, odor, texture, state etc. The pH was determined using a digital pH meter. Spreadability was assessed using glass slide under a fixed load. Viscosity was measured using Brookfield viscometer (spindle no.5,30rpm) at 25°C. Washability was observed by ease of removal of the formulation from glass slide under running tap water.

IN-VITRO ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY

Antibacterial activity of formulated hair pack was assessed against *Staphylococcus aureus* by the agar well diffusion method. Sterilized nutrient agar plates were inoculated with bacterial suspension. Ciprofloxacin was used as the standard. After incubation at room temperature, the zone of inhibition was measured and compared with standard.

IN-VITRO ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY

Antifungal activity of Hair Pack was tested using agar well diffusion method against *Candida albicans*. Potato Dextrose Agar plates were prepared and inoculated with fungal culture. Wells are bored and filled with the test sample. Clotrimazole was used as the standard antifungal agent. After incubation at room temperature, the zone of inhibition was measured and compared with standard.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING****Table 3: Phytochemical screening**

TESTS	NEEM	FENUGREEK
ALKALOIDS	+	+
CARBOHYDRATES	+	+
FLAVANOIDS	+	+
TRITERPENOIDS	+	-
SAPONINS	-	+
TANNINS	-	+

Figure no 1: Phytochemical screening**EVALUATION TEST FOR HERBAL HAIR PACK****Organoleptic Evaluation****Table 4: Organoleptic Evaluation**

SL. NO.	Parameters	Observation
1	Colour	Greenish brown
2	Odour	Characteristic lavender fragrance
3	State	Semi-solid
4	Texture	Smooth creamy

Figure no 2: Formulations

pH of the hair pack

The pH of the hair pack was determined by using standard digital pH meter at room temperature.

Table 5: pH of hair pack

SL. NO.	Formulations	pH
1	F1	6.3
2	F2	6.22
3	F3	6.33

Figure no 3: pH of hair pack

Spreadability

It was determined by applying the formulated hair pack on one glass slide and placing another glass slide over it. Then a required weight was applied to the upper glass slide. The spreadability of the formulated hair pack was found to spread evenly, in a time range of 4–10 second

Table 6: Spreadability

SL.NO.	Formulations	Spreadability (gm.cm/sec)
1	F1	12.5
2	F2	15.62
3	F3	13.75

Figure no 4: Spreadability**Washability**

The prepared herbal hair pack showed good washability by keeping the pack on the slide under running tap water. Washability was assessed based on the ease of removal and the presence or absence of residue on the slide.

Table 7: Washability

SL. NO.	Formulations	Washability
1	F1	Easily washable
2	F2	Easily washable
3	F3	Easily washable

Viscosity

The viscosity values of herbal hair pack range between 10,000 -35,000 cPs. The prepared product shows viscosity within a normal range.

Table 8: Viscosity

SL. NO.	Formulations	Viscosity (cP)
1	F1	25300
2	F2	31240
3	F3	24500

Figure no 5: Viscosity

***In vitro* Antibacterial activity of topical herbal hair pack**

Table 9: Antibacterial activity

SL. NO.	Formulations	Zone of inhibition (mm)
1	Control	22
2	F1	Less than 10
3	F2	16
4	F3	12

Figure no 6: Antibacterial Activity

In vitro* Anti-fungal Activity of Hair pack*Table 10: Antifungal activity**

SL. NO.	Formulations	Zone of inhibition(mm)
1	Control	21
2	F1	13
3	F2	15
4	F3	14

Figure no 7: Antifungal activity**DISCUSSION**

The project focuses on the formulation and evaluation of an anti-dandruff herbal hair pack using natural plant-based ingredients known for their anti-fungal, antibacterial properties. The herbs such as neem, fenugreek was selected based on literature review and traditional use in hair care. The selected herbal materials were primarily authenticated by a botanist to assure the quality and verification of plant material. Procurement of excipients were done. The Neem and Fenugreek decoction was prepared for the phytochemical screening and the tests were performed to detect the presence of tannins, flavonoids, alkaloids, triterpenoids, saponins, carbohydrates. Herbal hair pack was formulated by weighing the required quantities of neem powder, fenugreek powder, and multani mitti and passed through appropriate sieve. The powders were mixed uniformly in a mortar. Sodium benzoate was dissolved separately in a small quantity of distilled water and added to the powder mixture. Rose water and the remaining distilled water were added gradually with continuous trituration to obtain a smooth paste. Vitamin E was incorporated into the mixture with gentle stirring. Lavender oil was added at the final stage for fragrance. The prepared hair pack transferred into a suitable, well-labelled container. Organoleptic evaluation was conducted to assess the sensory characteristics of a product, such as its appearance, colour, odour, texture and overall sensory experience. The colour of the formulations was found to be greenish brown. All formulation has a characteristics odour of lavender oil. The hair pack had a smooth creamy texture. The prepared herbal hair pack was evaluated for pH, washability, spreadability, viscosity. The pH of the formulations F1, F2, F3 was measured using a digital pH meter and found to be 6.3, 6.22 and 6.33 respectively. These values fall within the optimal pH range. The spreadability of the formulations F1, F2, F3 are measured and found to be 12.5 gm.cm/sec, 15.62 gm.cm/sec, 13.75

gm.cm/sec. The washability test of the formulations was performed and the three formulations are easily washable. The viscosity of the formulations F1, F2, F3 was measured using Brookfield viscometer and found to be 25300 cP, 31240 cP, 24500cP. *In vitro* antibacterial and *In-vitro* anti-bacterial studies were carried out using *Staphylococcus aureus*. The *In-vitro* antibacterial study was performed by measuring the zone of inhibition of the product. Out of the three formulations F2 shows greater zone of inhibition. *In-vitro* anti-fungal test was conducted using Agar well-diffusion method and the fungus used was *Candida albicans* for evaluating the fungal growth and the zone of inhibition were measured. Out of the three formulations F2 shows greater zone of inhibition. As the product are made from natural ingredients and less amount of chemicals are present, they are safe to use.

CONCLUSION

The present study was focused on formulating and evaluating an herbal hair pack using selected natural ingredients possessing hair-nourishing, anti-bacterial, and anti-fungal properties. The formulation exhibited satisfactory physicochemical characteristics such as acceptable pH, good viscosity, spreadability, and washability, confirming its suitability for topical application on the scalp. The herbal hair pack demonstrated significant anti-bacterial and anti-fungal activity against selected test microorganisms, indicating its potential effectiveness in controlling dandruff, fungal scalp infections. and preventing bacterial growth. Overall, the results suggest that the formulated herbal hair pack is safe, effective, and economical, and can serve as a promising natural alternative to synthetic hair care products for improving hair health, reducing dandruff, and managing fungal scalp conditions. Further studies may be conducted to establish its clinical efficacy and long-term safety.

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